

TRENDS IN **HERITAGE SCIENCE**

DECLARATION AT THE FIRST UK NATIONAL HERITAGE SCIENCE CONFERENCE

10 July 2025

At the UK Heritage Science Conference, “Trends in Heritage Science”, held in London by the National Heritage Science Forum, participants from academic and heritage institutions across the UK and beyond, including professionals at all career stages and roles, came together to affirm the following:

- 1. Heritage plays a vital role in the resilience and success of societies.** It supports cultural identity, community cohesion, sustainable development, and a sense of belonging.
- 2. We live in uncertain and challenging times.** Global crises – social, environmental, political – are intensifying. The IPCC’s Scenario SSP3 threatens to become an apt description of the current political climate:

“In this world, countries increasingly focus on domestic or, at most, regional issues. Nationalist policies, concerns about competitiveness and security, and regional conflicts push countries to focus on self-sufficiency (...). Environmental policies are weak, and global challenges to mitigation and adaptation are high.” *IPCC AR6 Synthesis Report, Box 1.2, Scenario SSP3 (Regional Rivalry – A Rocky Road)*

- 3. In this context, Heritage Science must meet the challenge and demonstrate its capacity to strengthen heritage, and through it, society.**

Heritage Science exemplifies a collaborative model. The complexity of heritage-related problems demands interdisciplinary solutions: conservators work alongside chemists, computer scientists with archaeologists, policymakers with engineers.

This culture of partnership spans institutions such as universities, SMEs, museums, public bodies, business and commerce, and transcends borders through international collaborations.

- 4. With this inherent strength of our discipline and the UK’s strong tradition of collaborative research in mind, we make the following recommendations:**

- (a)** Enhance multidisciplinary heritage science research nationally and internationally, securing the UK’s sustained leadership.
- (b)** Openly welcome scientists from around the world, particularly from regions where scientific freedom is under threat, for the benefit of heritage science and the broader scientific community.
- (c)** Enhance the contribution of heritage science to major societal challenges, such as climate adaptation and social inclusion by deepening partnerships with technological and cultural industries and improving mechanisms for translating research into impact.

